

Developing methods for characterising flavour compounds in distilled spirits: Application to gin, rum and whisky

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Abstract

In order to develop an analytical technique to study aroma compounds applicable to all kinds of liquors, a model mixture embodying a theoretical distilled spirit was developed. This solution contains 25 of the most frequent flavour compounds found in these alcoholic drinks, classified in 15 chemical classes, at their mean concentrations. Liquid-liquid extraction (LLE), solid phase extraction (SPE), solid phase microextraction (SPME) and stir bar sorptive extraction/headspace sorptive extraction (SBSE/HSSE) were tested on the model mixture before analysis by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry/flame ionisation detection (GC-MS/FID). HS-SPME appeared to be the best compromise between efficiency, time and ease of use. The HS-SPME method optimised to the model mixture was successfully applied to 3 commercial samples.

Keywords: distilled spirit, analytical technique, model mixture, extraction, flavour compound

Introduction

The number and the popularity of craft distilleries has considerably increased over the last decade, resulting in a surge of innovative production processes offering new aromas and flavours for distilled spirits [1]. In order to characterise trials as part of research and development studies and to ensure batch-to-batch reproducibility through quality control processes, efficient, reliable, and fast analytical methods are needed.

Comte de Grasse is a company producing premium distilled spirits inspired by the extraction techniques used in perfumery. They intend to develop innovative and sustainable processes for the fermentation, distillation and ageing of liquors. With the aim of describing the flavour profile of their alcoholic drinks, analytical techniques applicable to all kinds of spirits are required.

Gas chromatography is the most frequently used method for the analysis of distilled spirits because it enables the identification of a large number of analytes and can be coupled to various detectors [2]. Some of the substances found in alcoholic beverages present at very low levels contribute significantly to the aroma profile of the beverage. When a classic chromatographic system is used (GC-FID or single quadrupole GC-MS), a concentration of the volatile fraction prior to analysis is necessary for their detection [3]. Thus, the selection and the optimization of an appropriate extraction method is critical.

To that end, a model mixture embodying a theoretical distilled spirit was developed. The model mixture was therefore submitted to 4 extraction techniques frequently described in literature for the concentration of flavour compounds in distilled spirits: liquid-liquid extraction (LLE), solid phase extraction (SPE), solid phase microextraction (SPME) and stir bar sorptive extraction/headspace sorptive extraction (SBSE/HSSE).

Experimental

Commercial samples of distilled spirits and chemicals

The rum (Diplomático Selección de Familia) and whisky (Glenfiddich 14 year bourbon barrel reserve) were bought at a local store. The gin sample (Comte de Grasse 44°N) was provided by Comte de Grasse. The compounds used to make the model mixture were obtained from commercial sources. Dichloromethane and acetonitrile (Merck) were freshly distilled prior to use. Ethanol (96% purity) was obtained from Isnard (Grasse, France).

Liquid-liquid extraction

The model mixture (50 mL) was mixed with deionised water (150 mL) and NaCl (20 g). Dichloromethane was added and it was put under stirring (500 rpm) for 10 min. at room temperature (3 x 60 mL). The organic phases were gathered, dried on MgSO₄, filtrated with a Büchner funnel and evaporated to 500 µL with a Kuderna-Danish concentrator. The extract was filtrated on a 0.22 µm syringe filter and stored at -18°C before analysis. Each trial was carried out in triplicate.

Solid phase extraction

The model mixture (12,5 mL) was mixed with deionised water (37,5 mL) and percolated through a Lichrolut EN 500 mg SPE cartridge (Merck) after conditioning with acetonitrile and equilibrating with an ethanol/water 9:1 (v/v) solution. Compounds of interest were eluted with dichloromethane (2 x 4 mL) which was evaporated to 500 μ L with a Kuderna-Danish concentrator.

Solid phase microextraction

Fibres and a manual SPME device were obtained from Supelco Co. (Bellefonte, PA). Fibres tested for extraction of the volatile components were as follows: poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) 100 μ m, carboxen/PDMS (CAR/PDMS) 85 μ m and divinylbenzene/CAR/PDMS (DVB/CAR/PDMS) 50/30 μ m. Before use, fibres were conditioned as recommended by the manufacturer. If necessary, the model mixture was diluted with deionised water to reduce the EtOH content. When needed, 1.3 g NaCl were added. 13 mL of a sample was then placed in a 40 mL amber vial closed by a PTFE/silicone septum (Supelco). Before extraction, the vial headspace was let to reach equilibrium for 24h at 25°C and 300 rpm. When extraction was not carried out at 25 °C, a water bath was used to control the temperature and the sample was conditioned during 5 minutes before extraction. Each analysis was carried out in triplicate. After exposure, the fibre was thermally desorbed into a GC and left in the injection port (equipped with a 0.75 mm i.d. inlet liner) for 5 min. The injector was set at the temperature recommended by the manufacturer and operated in splitless mode for 5 min.

Stir bar sorptive extraction / headspace sorptive extraction

Extractions were carried out with PDMS commercial stir bars (10mm length \times 0.5mm film thickness), supplied by Gerstel (Mülheim a/d Ruhr, Germany) as follows: a volume of 3.25 mL of sample and 9.25 mL of deionised water were placed in a 40 mL amber vial. The stir bar was then added to the flask or placed in the headspace. The vial was closed by a PTFE/silicone septum. The PDMS stir bar (or a standard stir bar for HSSE) was stirred at 800 rpm at 25°C for 60 min. After removal from the sample, PDMS stir bar was washed for a few seconds in distilled water and gently dried with a lint-free tissue. It was then transferred into a thermal desorption tube for thermal desorption. Before each extraction, the stir bar was conditioned at 300°C for 60 min.

Apparatus

LLE, SPE and SPME: These analyses were carried out using a 7820A/5977B GC-MS/FID (Agilent, Little Falls, DE, USA) equipped with an HP-5ms capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 μ m, Agilent). The temperature program was as follows: 40°C for 4 min, 40 to 220 °C at 2°C/min, 220 to 270°C at 8°C/min, holding for 7.25 min. The detection by the mass spectrometer was performed in the electron ionisation (EI) mode (70 eV ionisation energy). The acquisition was performed in scanning mode (mass range m/z 35–350 u). Identification of the aroma compounds was achieved by comparing the retention indices (RI) and mass fragmented patterns with those of reference compounds or with mass spectrums in commercial and homemade libraries and previously reported RI in the literature. Some of the identifications were confirmed by the injection of the chemical standards. Linear retention indices of the compounds were calculated using an n-alkane series.

SBSE/HSSE: The coated stir bars were thermally desorbed using an ATD-350 thermodesorption system (Perkin Elmer, Waltham, MA, USA) at 250°C for 15 min under a helium flow (50 mL min⁻¹) and the desorbed analytes were focused on a trap at -35°C. Finally, the trap was programmed from -35°C to 300°C (held for 3 min) at 20°C s⁻¹ for analysis by GC-MS. Capillary GC-MS analyses mode were performed using an Clarus 680 - SQ 8T system (Perkin Elmer), equipped with an Elite-5ms capillary column (30 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 μ m, Perkin). The temperature program was as follows: 40 to 220 °C at 2°C/min, 220 to 270°C at 8°C/min, holding for 6.25 min. The detection by the mass spectrometer was performed in the electron ionisation (EI) mode (70 eV ionisation energy). The acquisition was performed in scanning mode (mass range m/z 35–350 u). Identification of the aroma compounds was achieved by comparing mass fragmented patterns with mass spectrums in commercial and homemade libraries.

Results and discussion

Model mixture

A literature study led to the identification of 15 chemical classes usually found in liquors. For each class, at least one of the most recurrent compounds was chosen and put in the mixture at its mean concentrations in distilled spirits. Additional compounds were added in order to study the influence of the chemical structure on the extraction (chain length, aromaticity, presence of a cycle). An important ratio (x20000) was noticed between the extreme concentration values (sotolon – 0.00093 mg L⁻¹, furfural – 18.2 mg L⁻¹).

Table 1: Composition of the model mixture.

Compound	Concentration (mg/L)	Mean odour threshold in water (mg/L)*
hexanal	0.132	0.0501
furfural	18.2	9.602
o-xylene	0.313	0.45
α -pinene	4.02	0.296
benzaldehyde	7.98	1.72
dimethyl trisulfide	0.0595	0.00003
2-octanone	0.261	0.0418
ethyl hexanoate	17.4	0.00186
trimethylpyrazine	0.154	0.216
hexanoic acid	1.39	4.145
1,1,3-triethoxypropane	0.103	3.70 ^a
linalool	5.28	0.0108
2-phenylethanol	7.31	1.331
sotolon	0.000938	0.00565
diethyl succinate	3.78	353 ^a
2-phenylethyl acetate	0.457	0.249
decanol	0.114	0.047
<i>cis</i> -whiskey lactone	0.69	0.035 ^b
<i>trans</i> -whiskey lactone	0.31	0.05 ^c
decanoic acid	5.56	5.464
(E)- β -damascenone	0.0469	0.00125
ethyl decanoate	7.45	1.299
vanillin	2.86	0.301
β -caryophyllene	0.679	0.461
<i>cis</i> -nerolidol	0.0387	0.1

*from van Gemert, L.J. et al (2011)

Extraction technique comparison

A pre-optimisation study identified dichloromethane as the most efficient solvent for LLE (with NaCl addition), and ethylvinylbenzene-divinylbenzene copolymer as the most suitable sorbent for SPE. Among the four tested extraction techniques, LLE gave the best results as it enabled to detect 23 out of the 25 compounds in the mixture. Two compounds were not detected because of either a low concentration (sotolon – 0.000938 mg/L) or a poor response with apolar columns (hexanoic acid). This technique is however significantly time, solvent and sample consuming. The efficiency of SPE in terms of compounds detected was lower than that of LLE. SBSE and HSSE gave slightly better results (22 compounds detected) than SPME (21 compounds detected), which could be explained by the fact that stir bars have a larger coating volume than SPME fibres. However, SPME can be fully automated while the stir bar extractions have to be carried out manually [4]. SPME was thus chosen as the preferred method of extraction and was further optimised.

Table 2: Results obtained by applying different extraction techniques to the model mixture.

Extraction technique	Detected compounds (/25)	Handling time	Sample amount	Solvent amount
LLE	23	3 h	50 mL	200 mL
SPE	17	1 h	13 mL	10 mL
SPME	21	0.2 h	3 mL	-
SBSE	22	0.2 h	3 mL	-
HSSE	22			

SPME condition optimisation

DVB/CAR/PDMS in headspace mode was more efficient than CAR/PDMS (headspace) and PDMS (headspace and immersion) fibre types. Reducing the ethanol strength from 40 to 10% volume increased the number of compounds detected, a result in agreement with previous reports [5]. The addition of sodium chloride led to better results, which could be explained by the salting-out effect. Optimal time and temperature conditions were determined by studying specifically the peak area of furfural, α -pinene, (E)- β -damascenone and β -caryophyllene, four compounds of the model mixture covering a fairly wide range of polarities and volatilities. A kinetic monitoring showed that at least 1 hour extraction was necessary to get a satisfactory signal to noise ratio for (E)- β -damascenone, and to reach equilibrium for α -pinene and furfural. Varying the temperature between room

temperature and 45 °C revealed that except for (E)- β -damascenone, all peak areas were highest at a temperature of 30 °C. Because the largest peak area for (E)- β -damascenone was found to be slightly higher at 45 °C than at 30 °C, the optimum value for the temperature was set to 35°C.

Figure 1: SPME time and temperature optimisation.

Analysis of gin, rum and whisky samples by HS-SPME-GC-FID/MS

The optimised SPME method was then applied to 3 commercial samples which were analysed with a GC-MS/FID. Most compounds identified in the gin sample were terpenes, which utterly reflects the production process as this product was obtained by maceration and distillation of 13 botanicals in a water/ethanol mixture. The analysis of the rum and whisky samples enabled to identify 32 and 43 esters respectively which are quality markers in distilled spirits [6]. On the other hand, a higher number of phenols and furans was somehow expected as these 2 spirits have been oak-aged for several years, but this could be solved by the use of a polar column.

Table 3: Number of volatile compounds by chemical class identified in 3 commercial liquors analysed by HS-SPME-GC-MS/FID.

Chemical classes	44°N gin	Diplomatico rum	Glenfiddich whisky
alcohols	0	5	9
esters	10	32	43
lactones	0	1	2
carbonyls	3	4	7
acetals	1	2	2
acids	1	0	2
phenols	1	3	0
furans	1	1	2
aromatics	4	2	4
monoterpenes	19	1	1
oxygenated monoterpenes	26	1	0
sesquiterpenes	30	1	0
oxygenated sesquiterpenes	17	1	1
others	9	7	1
Total	122	61	74

Conclusion

The use of a model mixture allowed for the development of an analytical method applicable to three different kinds of distilled spirits. It enabled the comparison of four extraction techniques and the optimisation of SPME conditions which were successfully applied to commercial samples. Dynamic headspace method (Purge and Trap) will soon be developed and compared to the other four concentration methods.

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